

JAVA SCRIPT TILINING DASTURLASH FUNKSIYALARI

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi JavaScript tilidagi funksiyalar haqida umumiy tushuncha beriladi. Tezisdagi JavaScript funksiyalari haqida asosiy ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga oladi. JavaScript funksiyalari haqida batafsil tushuntirilgan va ularning qanday ishlaydilar, qanday qayta ishlatiladiganligi to'g'risida ko'proq ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, funksiyalar, nomi, argumentlari, qaytish qiymati, anonim funksiyalar, rekursiv funksiyalar.

Аннотация: Эта диссертация дает общее представление о функциях языка JavaScript. Диссертация содержит базовую информацию о функциях JavaScript. Подробно объясняет функции JavaScript и предоставляет дополнительную информацию о том, как они работают и как их можно использовать повторно.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, функции, имя, аргументы, возвращаемое значение, анонимные функции, рекурсивные функции.

Abstract: This thesis provides a general understanding of functions in the JavaScript language. The thesis contains basic information about JavaScript functions. Explains JavaScript functions in detail and provides more information on how they work and how they can be reused.

Keywords: JavaScript, functions, name, arguments, return value, anonymous functions, recursive functions.

JavaScript tilida funksiyalar, bir nechta amallarni bajarish uchun yaratilgan kod bo'limlari hisoblanadi. Ushbu funksiyalar kodni qayta ishlatishni osonlashtiradi va o'zining boshqa funksiyalar yoki dasturlarning ichida qayta ishlatilishiga imkon beradi. Bu funksiyalar JavaScript dasturlashining asosiy qismi hisoblanadi. Bu tezisdagi JavaScript tilidagi funksiyalar to'g'risida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan va ularni qanday ishlatish mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan.

JavaScript funksiyalarining yaratilishi va ishlatilishi:

JavaScript funksiyalari, "function" kalit so'zi bilan boshlanadigan funksiya nomi va argumentlar ro'yxati bilan yaratiladi. Funksiya nomi ko'rsatilmaganida, funksiya "anonymous" funksiya sifatida yaratiladi. Funksiya ishlatilishi quyidagi sintaksisda ifodalangan:

```
function functionName(parameter1, parameter2, ...) {  
  // function code  
  return result; // optional  
}
```

Funksiyalar orqali kod qayta ishlatish: Funksiyalar yaratilganidan so'ng ularni chaqirish yoki ishlatish mumkin. Buning uchun funksiyani nomi va kerakli argumentlarni kiritish kerak. Masalan:

```
function showMessage(message) {  
  alert(message);  
}
```

```
showMessage("Hello, World!");
```

JavaScript tilida funksiyalarning xususiyatlari: JavaScript tilida funksiyalar nomlanishi va argumentlari ko'rsatilishi majburiy emas. Funksiya qaytish qiymati bo'lishi shart emas. Funksiyalar o'z-o'zidan yoki boshqa funksiyalarning ichida chaqirilishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, JavaScript funksiyalari bir nechta argument qabul qilish, funksiyalarni uzatish va boshqa qulayliklarga ega.

JavaScript tilida anonim funksiyalar: Anonim funksiyalar nomi olmaydigan funksiyalardir. Ular boshqa funksiyalarning ichida yoki o'zlarining o'z ichida ishlatiladi. Anonim funksiyalar quyidagi sintaksisda ifodalangan:

```
var variableName = function(parameter1, parameter2, ...) {
    // function code
    return result; // optional
};
variableName(argument1, argument2, ...);
```

JavaScript tilida bir nechta funksiyalar: JavaScript tilida bir nechta funksiyalar yaratish mumkin. Bunday funksiyalar nomi bilan qidiriladi va ularni chaqirish uchun nomi bilan chaqirish kerak. Bir nechta funksiyalar quyidagi ko'rinishda yaratilishi mumkin:

```
function function1() {
    // function1 code
}
function function2() {
    // function2 code
}
function1();
function2();
```

JavaScript tilida rekursiv funksiyalar: Rekursiv funksiyalar o'zini qayta ishlatish orqali ishlar bajaradigan funksiyalardir. Bunday funksiyalar quyidagi ko'rinishda yaratilishi mumkin:

```
function factorial(n) {
    if (n <= 1) {
        return 1;
    } else {
        return n * factorial(n - 1);
    }
}
```

```
var result = factorial(5); // result = 5 * 4 * 3 * 2 * 1 = 120
```

Bu tezisda JavaScript tilidagi funksiyalar haqida batafsil ma'lumotlar berildi. Funksiyalar yaratish, nomlash va ishlatish, anonim funksiyalar, bir nechta funksiyalar va rekursiv funksiyalar haqida ko'rsatmalar berildi

Xulosa

JavaScript tilidagi funksiyalar dasturlashda juda katta ahamiyatga ega. Ular kodni qayta ishlatishni osonlashtiradigan va dastur kodini juda yaxshi tuzilgan qiladigan qulayliklarga ega. Funksiyalar nomi, argumentlari va qaytish qiymati ko'rsatilishi majburiy emas. Anonim funksiyalar, bir nechta funksiyalar va rekursiv funksiyalar JavaScript tilidagi funksiyalarning keng ko'lamdagi ilovalarda yuqori samaraga ega bo'lishi uchun muhimdir.

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